

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: MARU****FIRST NAME: YETIMGETA****PROGRAM CODE: DDIA****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: Microsoft Word 365 on Windows 10

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. Which one of the following represents pure research?
 - It addresses a conceptual problem that does have practical consequences.
 - Academic research done without any kind of bias.
 - It addresses a conceptual problem that does not have any direct practical consequences, when it only improves the understanding of a community of researchers.¹**
 - A research work without any plagiarism.

¹ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 8th ed. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 29.

2. Using the Turabian notes-bibliography citation style, how do you reference a journal article consulted online?

Author's Last Name, Author's First Name. Year of Publication. "Title of Article: Subtitle of Article." Title of Journal Volume Number, Issue Number (Additional Date Information): YY–YY.

Author's Last Name, Author's First Name. Year of Publication. "Title of Article: Subtitle of Article." *Title of Journal* Volume Number, Issue Number (Additional Date Information): YY–YY. URL.²

Author's Last Name. Year of Publication. "Title of Article: Subtitle of Article." Title of Journal Volume Number, Issue Number (Additional Date Information): YY–YY. URL.

Author's Last Name, Author's First Name. Year of Publication. Title of Book: Subtitle of Book. Edition Number ed. Place of Publication: Publisher's Name.

3. Postpositivism can be best explained as

It is the thinking that developed from logical positivism, a school of thought that maintains that all knowledge can be derived from direct observation and logical inferences based on that observation.³

It is not committed to any one research philosophy or paradigm.

² Kate L. Turabian, 233.

³ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2019), 147.

- It is contextually based and typically employs both quantitative and qualitative approaches to understand the problem.
 - It has a clear focus on social justice and includes feminist perspectives, racialized discourses, queer theory, trans theory, and disability inquiry.
4. Introduction is an important chapter in a dissertation. Which one of the following best expresses its purpose?
- It is an overview of the purpose and focus of the study, why it is significant, how it was conducted, and how it will contribute to professional knowledge and practice.⁴**
 - It indicates the need for the study, describes the issue or problem to be studied, and situates this within a broader social context.
 - It is the major objective or intent of the study.
 - It delineates the scope of the study.
5. According to the European Commission English style guide, how are footnote/endnote references formatted?
- It should be placed after any punctuation
 - The reference should normally be a superscript Arabic numeral – other symbols (such as asterisks or lower-case letters) should only be used in special**

⁴ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, 74.

cases. It should be placed before any punctuation, and should not be in bold or italic (even in headings).⁵

- Any types of numbers or letters can be utilized but they should be used sequentially and italicized.
- They should be formatted according to the style used by the standard MLA approach.

6. What is a working hypothesis?

- An argument to support a hypothesis.
- Good reasons and evidence to back up a hypothesis.
- An imagined tentative answer for a given research question⁶**
- A claim in a research process

7. In order to avoid plagiarism, the solution is to properly cite the author or source that has provided the information you are using. However, in some instances citations may not be necessary; so, when do we not cite something?

- When taking someone's idea without fully copying it
- When the information you are writing about is common knowledge that can be found in numerous areas⁷**

⁵ European Commission, *English Style Guide: A handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, 8th ed. (Brussels: European Commission, 2021), 62.

⁶ Kate L. Turabian, 58.

⁷ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 4th ed. (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 29.

- Taking passages from your own previous works
 - Re-writing someone else's work
8. Chapter of a dissertation which situates the study in the context of previous research and scholarly material pertaining to the topic, presents a critical synthesis of empirical literature according to relevant themes or variables, justifies how the study addresses a gap or problem in the literature, and outlines the theoretical or conceptual framework of the study. L77
- Analysis, Interpretation, and Synthesis
 - Conclusions and recommendations
 - Literature review⁸**
 - Methodology and research approach
9. Which one of the following implies a research paradigm?
- A set of conceptual problems to be analyzed and resolved by particular research.
 - A basic set of beliefs and assumptions that guide action of the researcher.⁹**
 - The processes for studying knowledge.
 - The values that go into knowing what we know.
10. From the different essential paradigms that inform qualitative research, ethnography can be best explained by;

⁸ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, 77.

⁹ Ibid., 146.

- It is an explanatory scheme comprising a set of concepts related to each other through logical patterns of connectivity.
- It is an in-depth exploration from multiple perspectives of the richness and complexity of a bounded social phenomenon (or multiple phenomena), be this a social unit or system such as a program, event, institution, organization, or community.
- It investigates the meaning of the lived experience of people to identify the core essence of human experience or phenomena as described by research participants.
- It is a form of qualitative research focused on discovering and describing the culture of a group of people and learning what it is like to be a member of the group from the perspectives of the members themselves.¹⁰**

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 4th ed. Bangui: Euclid University, 2021.

¹⁰ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2019), 164.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.